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» ABSTRACTS

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by vitrification using a cryoprotectant solution containing 1M sucrose, 2M glycerol, and 2.5M ethylene glycol in MS. For rewarming, cryovials with samples were plunged into a water bath (40°C) within two minutes. Explants were rinsed with washing solution consisted of MS medium supplemented with 0.3 M sucrose. To determine the effect of phytohormones on growth of meristems after the storage in liquid nitrogen two options of solid nutritive media for re-culturing were investigated: (1) MS medium with 0.5 mg/L 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP) + 0.1 mg/L indoleacetic acid (IAA), (2) MS medium with 0.5 mg/L kinetin + 0.1 mg/L IAA.

The results showed that the cryoprotectant solution used was non-toxic to the explants and provided a high level of survival. The spring cultivar 'Manuilivskiy' demonstrated an average regeneration rate of 56%, while the winter cultivar 'Diushes' achieved 45% after cryopreservation. Our results demonstrated that explants size significantly influenced post-thaw viability. Shoot tips measuring 2–3 mm achieved the highest survival rates (60 – 70%), making them the optimal choice for cryopreservation. Larger explants (3.5–4 mm) displayed strong regenerative potential but exhibited low viability (less than 25%). In contrast, smaller explants (1–1.5 mm) showed reduced viability (30 – 47%) and regenerative capacity, while 0.5 mm shoot tips failed to regenerate. Phytohormonal composition significantly influenced post-thaw recovery. Kinetin (0.5 mg/L) proved to be the most effective phytohormone, promoting better regeneration rates compared to BAP (0.5 mg/L). The study highlights the importance of explant size selection and hormone composition in ensuring successful cryopreservation outcomes.

This research offers valuable insights into optimizing cryopreservation protocols for vegetatively propagated crops, which are crucial for agricultural sustainability and biodiversity conservation.

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VP6 EVALUATING AFPI SUITABILITY TO ENHANCE POST-THAW FERTILITY IN NATIVE CHICKEN SPERM

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Sperm from indigenous breeds of chicken often exhibit increased sensitivity to cryoinjury, making them good models for optimizing cryopreservation protocols. The present study evaluated the effect of AFPI on the cryoresistance of sperm from the native breed Yellow Hungarian (YH). Pooled semen (10 pools/15 animals per pool) was frozen (dilution rate 1:3, 0.6M DMA, equilibration 1h at 5 °C, package 0.5 mL straws, cooling rate -100 °C/min) following supplementation of AFPI (1µg/mL). In order to discard changes in fertility induced by the presence of AFPI, control artificial inseminations (AI) (4, twice weekly), with non-frozen semen, were performed in 5 groups using: A (neat semen), B (A, extended in ASG, chilled 1h 5°C), C (B+DMA), D (B+AFPI) and E (B+DMA+AFPI). Sperm parameters and fertility were analysed using ANOVA with Tukey's test and the Chi-square test, respectively. Fertility rates obtained were 48.2%, 3.7%, 31.4%, 21.4% and 16.1%, respectively. There was a serious decrease in fertility of sperm chilled in ASG diluent alone (3.7%,) compared to neat semen (48.2, $p < 0.001$). On the other hand, semen containing DMA, AFPI or AFPI-DMA showed higher fertility than B ($p < 0.005$), indicating they play a protective role. Sperm frozen with AFPI-DMA resulted in higher proportion of sperm with intact DNA (70.2 ± 4.6 vs 49.1 ± 4.5 , $p < 0.05$); however, AI (8 in three weeks) gave only 1.5% of fertility rate. It is important to consider that the fertility reported by AI using the combination AFPI-DMA in non-frozen semen represented only one third of the fertility obtained with NS, indicating that 2 thirds had already been lost during the cooling/chilling phase. Therefore, the low fertility rate obtained with F/T semen is not surprising. AFPI showed a partial protective role to avoid fertility loss induced by cooling/chilling; however, reducing this loss is necessary to properly evaluate the role of AFPI during freezing itself.

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VP7 UNRAVELLING OXIDATIVE STRESS AND GENETIC INTEGRITY DURING CRYOCONSERVATION OF *Saussurea lappa*: A CRITICALLY ENDANGERED MEDICINAL PLANT

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Saussurea lappa (Falc.) Lipsch is a well-recognized herb, endemic to the Himalayan region, and valued for its commercially important secondary metabolites. However, increasing demand, unscientific collection, and overharvesting have led to its depletion in the wild. Therefore, developing an effective protocol is crucial for its long-term conservation. This study aimed to establish a cryopreservation protocol for *S. lappa* shoot tips using the